

Statistical Relationship between the Parameters of Some Indexed Journals by Fuzzy Linear Regression

Pavan Kumar

Abstract: In this paper, we propose a statistical relationship between acceptance rate & first decision time of some indexed journals by applying fuzzy linear regression (FLR). We collect the data from two web sources: Elsevier journal finder, and Springer journal suggester. In this problem, we concentrate on the data of the acceptance rate and first decision time. To examine the relationship between these measures, we apply a statistical approach, which is based on correlation and regression analysis. We determine the relative error (RE) of the data collected. We plot the scatter diagram between the two measures. Pearson correlation coefficient (CC) value is also calculated. All this analysis reports that there is a moderate positive correlation between acceptance rate & first decision time.

Keywords: Acceptance rate, first decision time, Correlation, Fuzzy Linear Regression.

I. INTRODUCTION

In statistics, the correlation and regression analysis are very popular. Yen, K.K., Ghoshray, S., Roig, G., (1999) presented a linear regression model using triangular fuzzy number coefficients. Chang, Y.-H.O., Ayyub, B.M., (2001) presented the fuzzy regression methods-a comparative assessment. Natalie, M., & James, R. (2002) contemplated an improved batch means procedure for simulation output analysis. D'Urso, P., (2003) proposed the linear regression analysis for fuzzy/crisp input and fuzzy/crisp output data. Koenker, R. (2004) discussed the quantile regression for longitudinal data.

Fuzzy linear regression (FLR) has become a very large area of research. The idea of FLR builds on the fuzzy set theory developed by Zadeh (1965) and it was first introduced by Tanaka, Uejima, and Asai (1982). The concept behind FLR is that the deviations between the observed and estimated values are assumed to originate from imprecise observations or vague relations between the model variables. Modarres, M., Nasrabadi, E., Nasrabadi, M.M., (2005) discussed the fuzzy linear regression analysis from the point of view risk. Therefore, the uncertainty in FLR models is fuzziness (Chen & Hsueh (2007). Abdalla, A., Buckley, J.J., (2007) presented the Monte Carlo methods in fuzzy linear regression. Chen, L.H. and C.C. Hsueh, (2007) developed a mathematical programming method for formulating a fuzzy regression model based on distance criterion. Bargiela, A., Pedrycz, W., Nakashima, T., (2007) studied multiple regression with fuzzy data.

Canay, I.A. (2011) proposed a simple approach to quantile regression for panel data. Azagba, S., Sharaf, M. F. (2012) studied the fruit and vegetable consumption and body mass index by applying a quantile regression approach.

Wang, J. (2012) studied the bayesian quantile regression for parametric nonlinear mixed effects models. Osman, Z., & Sentosa, I. (2013) studied the mediating effect of customer satisfaction on service quality and customer loyalty relationship in Malaysia Rural Tourism. Qiu, Heting; Li, & Xuewei, (2013) presented a study of combined evaluation of suppliers based on correlation. Panigrahi, A., K., (2013) studied the relationship between inventory management and profitability by applying an empirical analysis of indian cement companies. Geraci, M. (2016) proposed the estimation of regression quantiles in complex surveys with data missing at random with the help of an application to birthweight determinants. Coulom, Jean Shenai, & Vijay, (2018) studied the effect of alternative measures of distance on the correlation of real effective exchange rate returns with the help of an approach to contagion analysis. Qiang Fu, Linqi Li, Mo Li, Tianxiao Li, Dong Liu, & Song Cui (2018) presented a simulation-based linear fractional programming model for adaptable water allocation planning in the main stream of the songhua river basin. They applied fractional programming approach for adaptable water allocation planning, which is located in the main stream of the songhua river basin in China country. Kumar, P. (2019) presented an inventory optimization model for quadratic increasing holding cost and linearly increasing deterministic demand, in crisp environment.

Motivation for this research work is to develop a mathematical formula for studying the acceptance rate and the number of days giving the first decision for reputed journals. To the best of our knowledge, there is no such mathematical formula in literature. To fill this gap, the contribution of the present work is justified.

In the present work, we study the relationship between the journal measures consisting of acceptance rate and first decision time. We discuss some basic concepts in section 2. In following section 3, we describe some notations. The proposed problem definition is presented in section 4. In the section 5, we give some numerical calculations to calculate the correlation coefficient, mean relative error and the straight line equation. In the last, we conclude the work in the section 6.

Revised Manuscript Received on September 15, 2019

Pavan Kumar, Department of Mathematics, Koneru Lakshmaiah Education Foundation, Vaddeswaram, Andhra Pradesh, INDIA- 22502, Email: pavankmaths@gmail.com

II. DEFINITIONS AND PRELIMINARIES

Fuzzy Set

A fuzzy set \tilde{A} on the given universal set X is a set of ordered pairs

$$\tilde{A} = \{(x, \mu_A(x)) : x \in X\}$$

where $\mu_A: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$, is called membership function. The α – cut of \tilde{A} , is defined by $A_\alpha = \{x: \mu_A(x) = \alpha, \alpha \geq 0\}$.

Fuzzy Number

A fuzzy number is a fuzzy set \tilde{A} with membership function $\mu_{\tilde{A}}: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$, with the following properties as real line R :

- (i) \tilde{A} is normal, i.e., there exists $x \in R$ such that $\mu_A(x) = 1$.
- (ii) \tilde{A} is piece-wise continuous.
- (iii) $\text{supp}(\tilde{A}) = \text{cl}\{x \in R: \mu_A(x) > 0\}$, where cl represents the closure of a set.
- (iv) \tilde{A} is a convex fuzzy set.

Triangular Fuzzy Number

A triangular fuzzy number $\tilde{A} = (a_1, a_2, a_3)$ is represented with membership function $\mu_{\tilde{A}}$ as:

$$\mu_{\tilde{A}}(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{x-a_1}{a_2-a_1}, & \text{for } a_1 \leq x < a_2; \\ 1, & \text{for } x = a_2; \\ \frac{a_3-x}{a_3-a_2}, & \text{for } a_2 < x \leq a_3; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Symmetric Triangular Fuzzy Number

If $a_2 = a_3$, then the triangular fuzzy number $\tilde{A} = (a_1, a_2, a_3)$ is called symmetric triangular fuzzy number.

Graded Mean Integration Representation Method for Defuzzification

If $\tilde{A} = (a_1, a_2, a_3)$ is a triangular fuzzy number, then graded mean integration representation of \tilde{A} is given by

$$P(\tilde{A}) = \frac{a_1 + 4a_2 + a_3}{6} \quad (2)$$

Karl Pearson Correlation Coefficient:

Correlation analysis is an attempt to measure the strength of relationships between two variables. This is measured by means of a single number, which is called a correlation coefficient (CC). CC measures the strength of the linear association between x and y . Karl Pearson correlation coefficient (CC), denoted by r between x and y :

$$r = \frac{n \sum xy - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{n \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2} \sqrt{n \sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2}} \quad (3)$$

When CC is near to -1 or +1, there are strong linear relations.

Relative Error (RE)

The RE reflects the credibility of the proposed method, and is calculated by the formula [Qiang Fu, et al. (2018)]:

$$RE = \frac{|y-x|}{x} \times 100 \% \quad (4)$$

Scatter Diagram:

It is a pictorial representation of the data, which demonstrates us the direction of the relationship between two variables. When the pair of values (x_i, y_i) for $i=1, 2, \dots, n$ are plotted on a two-dimensional plane, the points show the pattern in which they actually lie. Such a diagram or pattern is known as scatter diagram. If these points lie on a straight line, it is expected that there is a linear relationship between x and y , otherwise not.

Notations

In this manuscript, following notations are:

- x : Time from Submission to first decision,
- y : Acceptance rate, in %.
- \tilde{x} : Fuzzy number
- \tilde{y} : Fuzzy number
- CC: Karl Pearson correlation coefficient (r)
- RE: Relative error
- \overline{RE} : Mean relative error
- $\sum x$: Sum of all x terms.

III. APPLICATION PROBLEM DEFINITION

We want to calculate the how the acceptance rate (y) in percentage is related with the first decision time (x) in days. For that we plot a scatter diagram to know the regression is linear or non-linear. Also, we calculate the Karl Pearson correlation coefficient. We collected the real data for 39 indexed journals dated 31-03-2019, as given below in Table 1, from the following web sources:

- Web Source (i) Elsevier Journal Finder, link: <https://journalfinder.elsevier.com>
- Web Source (ii) Springer Journal Suggester/Finder, link: <https://journalsuggester.springer.com>

Table 1: Nemerical Date Collected from Sources (i) & (ii)

Journal	Abstracts & Indexing	Time from Submission to First decision,	Time from Submission to first decision, (x) in days	Acceptance Rate (AR) In % (y)
Applied Mathematics Letters	SCOPUS, ESCI	1 week	7	11
Decision Support Systems	SCOPUS, ESCI, SCI	3 weeks	21	11
Information Processing & Management	SCOPUS, SCI	3 weeks	21	9
Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation	SCOPUS, SCI	4 weeks	28	15
Expert Systems with Applications	SCOPUS, SCIE	5 weeks	35	13
Knowledge-Based Systems	SCOPUS, SCI,	6 weeks	42	17
Operations Research Letters	SCOPUS, SCIE	8 weeks	56	26
Int. J. of Approximate Reasoning	SCOPUS, ESCI, SCI,	8 weeks	56	30
Neurocomputing	SCOPUS, SCIE	9 weeks	63	29
Computers & Operations Research	SCOPUS, SCI	9 weeks	63	14

Applied Mathematical Modelling	SCOPUS, SCI	9 weeks	63	17
Applied Soft Computing	SCOPUS, SCI	8 weeks	56	16
Information Sciences	SCOPUS, SCI	8 weeks	56	19
Omega	SCOPUS, SCI	6 weeks	42	12
Information Fusion	SCOPUS, SCI	8 weeks	56	19
Journal of Manufacturing Systems	SCOPUS, SCI	6 weeks	42	15
Journal of The Franklin Institute	SCOPUS, SCI	11 weeks	77	31
Applied Energy	SCOPUS, SCI	5 weeks	35	14
Operations Research Perspectives	SCOPUS, SCI	5 weeks	35	13
Int. J. on Interactive Design and Manufacturing	SCOPUS, ESCI	16 days	16	39
Palgrave Communications	SCOPUS, ESCI	40 days	40	38
Applied Intelligence	SCOPUS, SCI-E	19 days	19	19
Computational Optimization and Applications	SCOPUS, SCI, SCI-E	45 days	45	14
J. of Global Optimization	SCOPUS, SCI, SCI-E	60 days	60	24
EURO Journal on Computational Optimization	SCOPUS, SCI	67 days	67	27
Optimization Letters	SCOPUS, SCIE	77 days	77	26
Japan Journal of Industrial and Applied Mathematics	SCOPUS, SCI, SCI-E	86 days	86	32
Int. J. of System Assurance Engineering and Management	SCOPUS, ESCI	127 days	127	47
J. of Industrial Engineering International	SCOPUS	109 days	109	23
Int. J. of Applied & Computational Mathematics	SCOPUS	76 days	76	38
Int. Journal of Fuzzy Systems	SCOPUS, SCI-E	48 days	48	22
J. of the Operations Research Society of China	SCOPUS, ESCI	99 days	99	43
Queueing Systems	SCOPUS, SCI,	95 days	95	44
Int. Journal of Dynamics & Control	SCOPUS	60 days	60	35
J. of Intelligent Manufacturing	SCOPUS, SCI-E	32 days	32	12
J. of Optimization Theory and Applications	SCOPUS, SCI, SCI-E,	60 days	60	18
Annals of Data Science	Non-ESCI.	61 days	61	63
Granular Computing	Non-SCOPUS,	30 days	30	42
Bulletin of the Iranian Mathematical Society	SCOPUS, SCIE	20 days	20	32

IV. NUMERICAL CALCULATIONS

We take the data from the Table 1, for the variables x and y. To determine the correlation coefficient (CC), r, and RE, we prepare the following Table 2 as below:

Table 2: Data for the Determination CC, and RE.

x	y	xy	x ²	y ²	RE= $\frac{ y-x }{x} \times 100\%$
7	11	77	49	121	57.14
21	11	231	441	121	47.61
21	9	189	441	81	57.14
28	15	420	784	225	46.42
35	13	455	1225	169	62.85
42	17	714	1764	289	59.52

Statistical Relationship between the Parameters of Some Indexed Journals by Fuzzy Linear Regression

56	26	1456	3136	676	53.57
56	30	1680	3136	900	46.42
63	29	1827	3969	841	34.00
63	14	882	3969	196	49.00
63	17	1071	3969	289	73.01
56	16	896	3136	256	71.42
56	19	1064	3136	361	66.07
42	12	504	1764	144	71.42
56	19	1064	3136	361	66.07
42	15	630	1764	225	64.28
77	31	2387	5929	961	59.74
35	14	490	1225	196	60.00
35	13	455	1225	169	62.85
16	39	624	256	1521	143.75
40	38	1520	1600	1444	5.00
19	19	361	361	361	0
45	14	630	2025	196	68.88
60	24	1440	3600	576	60.00
67	27	1809	4489	729	59.70
77	26	2002	5929	676	66.23
86	32	2752	7396	1024	63.79
127	47	5969	16129	2209	62.99
109	23	2507	11881	529	78.89
76	38	2888	5776	1444	50.00
48	22	1056	2304	484	54.16
99	43	4257	9801	1849	56.56
95	44	4180	9025	1936	51.00
60	35	2100	3600	1225	41.66
32	12	384	1024	144	62.50
60	18	1080	3600	324	70.00
61	63	3843	3721	3969	3.27
30	42	1260	900	1764	40.00
20	32	640	400	1024	60.00
$\sum x=2081$	$\sum y=969$	$\sum xy=57794$	$\sum x^2=138015$	$\sum y^2=30009$	$\sum RE=2206.91$

Substituting all the summation values from Table 2 in equation (3), the value of correlation coefficient r is determined:

$$r = + 0.4813 \quad (5)$$

Mean value of RE is given by

$$\overline{RE} = \frac{\sum RE}{n} = \frac{2206.91}{39} = 56.58 \% \quad (6)$$

This shows that there is a $+ve$ correlation between x (time from submission to first decision, in days) and y (acceptance rate, in %). The strength of this correlation is not so strong, and not so weak, rather is moderate correlation. Scatter diagram is platted as given in Figure 1.

Crisp Least Square Fit of a Straight Line Method

Now we are going to fit a straight line between x and y .

The straight line equation is $y = ax + b$

From table (2), we have following values:

$$\sum x = \text{Sum of } x = 2081$$

$$\sum y = \text{Sum of } y = 969$$

$$\text{Mean } X = 53.359, \text{ Mean } Y = 24.8462$$

$$\text{Sum of squares } (SS_x) = 26974.9744$$

$$\text{Sum of products } (SP) = 6089.1538$$

$$b = SP/SS_x = 6089.15/26974.97$$

$$= 0.22573.$$

$$a = M_y - bM_x$$

$$= 24.85 - (0.23 * 53.36) = 12.80125.$$

Regression Equation:

$$y = 0.22573x + 12.80125 \quad (7)$$

Figure 1: Scatter Diagram

Figure 2: Straight Line Graph

Some Particular Cases

We discuss the following particular cases:

Case 1:

Determination of y, when x=10

By equation (6), we obtain

$$y = 0.22573(10) + 12.80125 = 13 \quad (8)$$

When the time from submission to first decision is 10 days, the acceptance rate would be 13 %.

Case 2:

Determination of y, when x=300

By equation (6), we obtain

$$y = 0.22573(300) + 12.80125 = 80.52 \quad (9)$$

When the time from submission to first decision is 300 days, the acceptance rate would be 80.52 %.

Fuzzy Least Square Fit of a Straight Line Method

Consider the n-data points $(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots (x_n, y_n)$, from an experiment. We fit a straight line by using symmetric triangular fuzzy numbers (STFN) in dependent and independent variables, as follows:

$$\tilde{y} = a\tilde{x} + b \quad (10)$$

Using (1), we find the n residuals \tilde{e}_i as:

$$\tilde{e}_i = y_i - \tilde{y}_i = y_i - (a\tilde{x}_i + b), \quad (11)$$

where $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

Sum of the squares of residuals \tilde{e}_i is given by

$$E = \sum_{i=1}^n \tilde{e}_i^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n [y_i - (a\tilde{x}_i + b)]^2 \quad (12)$$

E is a function of parameters 'a' and 'b'. We find 'a' and 'b' so that E is minimum. Necessary conditions for E to be minimum:

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial a} = 0, \text{ and } \frac{\partial E}{\partial b} = 0 \quad (13)$$

From (12) & (13), we obtain

$$\sum_{i=1}^n 2\tilde{x}_i [y_i - (a\tilde{x}_i + b)] = 0, \text{ i.e., } a \sum_{i=1}^n \tilde{x}_i^2 + b \sum_{i=1}^n \tilde{x}_i = \sum_{i=1}^n \tilde{x}_i y_i \quad (14)$$

$$\text{and } a \sum_{i=1}^n \tilde{x}_i + nb = \sum_{i=1}^n \tilde{y}_i \quad (15)$$

Equations (14) and (15) are fuzzy normal equations, which are to be solved to determine the required values for a and b. Substituting values of a and b in (10), we obtain the required fit of a straight line.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we determined a relationship between the first decision time, in days, and the acceptance rate, in percentages, for some indexed journals, by fuzzy linear

regression. This study is based on the real data, collected from the web sources of these journal publishers. The value of correlation coefficient is +0.4813, which represents a positive correlation, whose strength is moderate. The mean relative error (RE) is calculated to support the proposed approach. Additionally, we mathematically analyzed the regression statistical measure, which we found in linear trend. In the last, we conclude a linear relationship between these measures or parameters of the various journals. In this manuscript, a lot of information is given about the top indexed journals. This study may be very useful to the researchers in choosing a suitable journal as per acceptance rate and first decision time. Fuzzy and probabilistic nature of these measures may also be another dimension for further research work.

Conflicts of Interest: The author declares no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Zadeh, L. A. (1965). Fuzzy Sets, Information and Control, 8, 338-353.
2. Tanaka, H., Uejima, S. and Asai, K. (1982) Linear regression analysis with fuzzy model, IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man and Cybernetics, 12(6), 903-907.
3. Yen, K.K., Ghoshray, S., Roig, G., (1999). A linear regression model using triangular fuzzy number coefficients. Fuzzy Sets and Systems, 106, 167-177.
4. Chang, Y.-H.O., Ayyub, B.M., (2001). Fuzzy regression methods- a comparative assessment. Fuzzy Sets and Systems, 119, 187-203.
5. Natalie, M., & James, R. (2002). An improved batch means procedure for simulation output analysis, Management Science, 48(12), 1569-1586.
6. D'Urso, P., (2003). Linear regression analysis for fuzzy/crisp input and fuzzy/crisp output data. Computational Statistics and Data Analysis, 42, 47-72.
7. Koenker, R. (2004). Quantile regression for longitudinal data, Journal of Multivariate Analysis, 91(1), 74-89.
8. Modarres, M., Nasrabadi, E., Nasrabadi, M.M., (2005). Fuzzy linear regression analysis from the point of view risk. Int. J. Uncertainty, Fuzziness & Knowledge-Based Systems, 12, 635-649.
9. Abdalla, A., Buckley, J.J., (2007). Monte carlo methods in fuzzy linear regression. Soft Computing, 11, 991-996.
10. Chen, L.H. and C.C. Hsueh, (2007). A mathematical programming method for formulating a fuzzy regression model based on distance criterion. IEEE Trans. Syst. Man Cybern. Part B: Cybern., 137, 705-712.

11. Bargiela, A., Pedrycz, W., Nakashima, T., (2007). Multiple regression with fuzzy data. *Fuzzy Sets and Systems*, 158, 2169–2188.
12. Canay, I.A. (2011). A simple approach to quantile regression for panel data, *Econometr. Journal*, 14 (3), 368-386.
13. Azagba, S., Sharaf, M. F. (2012). Fruit and vegetable consumption and body mass index: a quantile regression approach, *Journal of Primary Care & Community Health*, 3(3), 210–220.
14. Wang, J. (2012). Bayesian quantile regression for parametric nonlinear mixed effects models, *Statistical Methods & Applns*, 21(3), 279-295.
15. Osman, Z., & Sentosa, I. (2013). Mediating effect of customer satisfaction on service quality and customer loyalty relationship in Malaysia Rural Tourism. *International Journal of Economics Business and Management Studies*, 2(1), 25-37.
16. Qiu, Heting; Li, & Xuwei, (2013). A study of combined evaluation of suppliers based on correlation, *Journal of Industrial Engineering & Management*, 6(1), 249-257.
17. Panigrahi, A., K., (2013). Relationship between inventory management and profitability: an empirical analysis of indian cement companies. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing & Management Review*, 2(7), 107-120.
18. Geraci, M. (2016). Estimation of regression quantiles in complex surveys with data missing at random: An application to birthweight determinants, *Statistical Methods in Medical Research*, 25(4), 1393-1421.
19. Coulom, Jean Shenai, & Vijay, (2018). The effect of alternative measures of distance on the correlation of real effective exchange rate returns: An approach to contagion analysis, *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 6(4), 1-18.
20. Qiang Fu, Linqi Li, Mo Li, Tianxiao Li, Dong Liu, & Song Cui (2018), A simulation-based linear fractional programming model for adaptable water allocation planning in the main stream of the songhua river basin, *China, Water*, 10(627); 1-18. doi:10.3390/w10050627
21. Web source Elsevier Journal Finder, link: <https://journalfinder.elsevier.com>
22. Web source Springer Journal Suggester/Finder, link: <https://journalsuggester.springer.com>
23. Kumar, P. (2019). Inventory optimization model for quadratic increasing holding cost and linearly increasing deterministic demand. *Int. Journal of Recent Technology & Engineering*, 7(6), 1999-2004.

AUTHOR PROFILE

PAVAN KUMAR is an Assistant Professor of Mathematics at the Koneru Lakshmaiah Education Foundation (K L University), Vaddeswaram (AP), India. He received his PhD (2014) in Operations Research, from NIT Warangal. He has published several research papers in international, national journals of high repute. His interests are mathematical programming, fuzzy optimization. His e-mail address is <pavankmaths@gmail.com>.

ORCID Dr. Pavan Kumar

 <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5340-7777>